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Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF DEPRESSION AMONG PATIENTS OF
DIABETES MELLITUS IN TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL**Dr Amina Tasarraf¹, Dr Mazia Shabbir², Dr Sana Maryam³^{1,2,3} Fatima Jinnah Medical University Lahore**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: We will assess depressive symptoms with diabetes on diabetes self-care treatment non adherence, functioning and health care.

Study Design: Cross sectional study

Place and Duration of Study: This study was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Sir Ganga Ram hospital Lahore from November, 2018 to October, 2019.

Materials and Methods: 120 patients both males and females were selected for this study. We administered a Questionnaire to 120 patients with type 1 and type 2 Diabetes, depressive symptoms, diabetes control, self-care. Assess the impact of depressive symptoms on adherence to diabetes self-care HbA1c levels functional impairment and health care.

Results: 120 cases were selected, 79 were males 41 were females, 25 pts were of type 1, 95 were of type 2. Depression was diagnosed using the structural clinical interview using Beck's Depression Inventory.

Conclusion: Findings demonstrate association of depression with diabetes clinical consideration, treatment non adherence, proper drug treatment of diabetes, depression, self-care and counseling mortality can be reduced with incidence of depression.

Key Words: Depression, Diabetes Mellitus, Complications, Glycemic control, Treatment, Quality of life.

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is chronic illness present in 2 to 5 percent population. Diabetes Mellitus is common problem, 180 million people affected with this disease worldwide.[1] This count can be doubled in 2030 [2]. There are two types of Diabetes Mellitus, type 1 and type 2. Insulin therapy for type 1, oral anti diabetic drugs for type 2 and for uncontrolled type 2 Diabetes Mellitus insulin therapy is recommended.

Depression is more in diabetic than in general population with poor quality of life,[3] patients with diabetes mellitus are 1.4 to 3 times to suffer from co morbid depression as compared to non-diabetic.[4] Uncontrolled diabetes Mellitus with Increase in blood glucose level incidence of complications are increased [5]. Depression in Diabetes Mellitus is due to non-adherence to treatment and self-care.[6]

Risk factors for Depression in Diabetes mellitus are younger age, female, unmarried or divorce and widow, lower socioeconomic level, poor glucose control low social support, low education level, complications of Diabetes mellitus, any medical co morbidity and past history of depression.[7] Risk of type 2 Diabetes Mellitus with Depressed Patients is reported to be as high as 1.6.[8]

Depressive symptoms are more in type 2 diabetic patients as compared to type 1 patients.[9] Depression is more noted in Diabetes Mellitus with complications as compared without complications in both type1 and type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.[10] With relationship between depression and diabetes depression may be risk factor for the onset of diabetes.[11] Increased risk of diabetes type 2 patients with depression is due to increased counterregulatory hormone release, disturbance in glucose transport function and raised immune inflammatory activation.[12] Insulin resistance and beta cell dysfunction result due to above physiological mechanism and development of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Poor glycemic control associated with depression in diabetes both type 1 and type 2 patients.[13]

High HbA1c level associate with depression in diabetes.[14] Depressive symptoms are associated with poor adherence to self-care particularly medications, diet and exercise.[15] In a review of treatment adherence among patients with depression in diabetes, it was observed relationship between depression and treatment nonadherence.[16]

Comorbid depression among patients with diabetes associated with less physical activity, unhealthy diet, and lower adherence to oral drugs, hypoglycemic, antihypertensives, and lipid lowering [17] Unsatisfactory metabolic control associated with psychiatric comorbidity, depression in diabetes associated with inadequate metabolic control in those patients with poor glycemic control despite good medical treatment. Consequently, poor disease control morbidity and mortality is increased [18].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was carried out in the Department of Medicine Sir Ganga Ram hospital Lahore from November, 2018 to October, 2019, this study was conducted to observe depression in diabetes with other complications of diabetes in a population poor adherence to treatment and quality of life. Informed consent was taken from the patients. Questionnaire was given to all patients. Data collected according to Questionnaire. Depression was assessed using structural clinical interview using Beck s Depression Inventory on separate questionnaire.

Level of depression according BDI

Total score	Level of Depression
1-10	These ups and downs are considered normal
11-16	Mild mood disturbance
17-20	Border line clinical Depression
21-30	Moderate Depression
31-40	Severe Depression
Over 40	Extreme Depression

Inclusion criteria was as males and females age 12ys to 60ys and depressed patients with DM type 1 and 2. Exclusion Criteria was as age below 12 years and above 60 years, Severe Psychotic illness and Severe medical illness. In order to get correct information Questionnaire was translated into Urdu.

RESULTS:

120 cases were selected for this study 79 were males 41 were females 90 patients belonged to Rural areas 30 belonged to Arabian areas. 20 patients were having age between 12-24 years, 31 patients age was among 25-40 years and 69 patients were having the age 41-60 years. Educational status, marital status, occupation and Socioeconomic status of the patients is given below in the tabular form.

Table No 01: Gender distribution

Gender	Qty	% age
Male	79	65.83%
Female	41	34.17%
Total	120	100%

Table No 02: Different statuses of patients

Educational Status		
Illiterate		56
Primary		19
Middle		15
Metric		9
Intermediate		7
Graduation		6
Masters		8
Depression as per marital status		
Married		83
Single		8
Widow		19
Divorced		10
Depression as per occupation		
Farmer		64
House wife		26
Unemployed		10
Service		7
Business		5
Laborer		8
Depression Socioeconomic status		
Lower		80
Middle		39
Upper		01
Investigations	RBS	Qty of patients
	140-185	60
	185-300	40
	300-450	20
HbA1c Levels	HbA1c	
	6.5	58
	7.5	32
	8.5	30

Table No 03: HbA1c Level Details

		FREQUENCY	PERCENT	VALID PERCENT	CUMULATIVE PERCENT
VALID	6.5	58	48.3	48.3	48.3
	7.5	32	26.7	26.7	75.0
	8.5	30	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Becks Depression Scale status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	19.00	1	.8	.8	.8
	20.00	3	2.5	2.5	2.5
	21.00	1	.8	.8	.8
	23.00	1	.8	.8	.8
	24.00	2	1.7	1.7	1.7
	25.00	6	5.0	5.0	5.0
	26.00	4	3.3	3.3	3.3
	27.00	8	6.7	6.7	6.7
	28.00	29	24.2	24.2	24.2
	29.00	26	21.7	21.7	21.7
	30.00	36	30.0	30.0	30.0
	31.00	2	1.7	1.7	1.7
	32.00	1	.8	.8	.8
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	100.0

8.5 in 25 patients type 2 was present in 95 patients, diabetic ketoacidosis in 16 patients, diabetic foot in 70, diabetic retinopathy in 6, pulmonary TB 10, neuropathy 11 diabetic nephropathy 7. Statistical analysis was done on SPSS 20 version.

Table No 04: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	SD
Age in Groups	120	15.00	60.00	42.9583	12.24703
Random Blood Sugar level	120	160.00	450.00	254.5833	86.09078
HbA1c Level	120	6.5	8.5	7.267	.8274
Becks Depression Scale status	120	19.00	32.00	28.1750	2.35026
Valid N (listwise)					

Table No 05: HbA1c Level

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12.821	12	1.068	1.665	.085
Within Groups	68.646	107	.642		
Total	81.467	119			

Table No 06: Becks Depression Scale status by RBS

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	247.972	37	6.702	1.343	.136
Within Groups	409.353	82	4.992		
Total	657.325	119			

Table No 07: Becks Depression Scale status by HbA1c

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	10.495	2	5.247	.949	.390
Within Groups	646.830	117	5.528		
Total	657.325	119			

Table No 08: Paired Samples Correlations

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	HbA1c Level & Becks Depression Scale status	120	-.035	.704
Pair 2	Random Blood Sugar level & Becks Depression Scale status	120	-.006	.949

DISCUSSION:

Depression is common problem in diabetes prevalent and negative impact in clinical outcomes, quality of life, associated with increased mortality in DM. [19] The factors could explain the occurrence of depression in diabetes. Dietary restrictions, financial problems, treatment demands and hospitalization contribute to depression. Severe Depressive symptoms associated with less adherence to dietary recommendations. Depression associated with high level of HbA1c level. Depression in Diabetes mellitus is higher in younger as compared with older age [20]. It has been found that patients with Depression in diabetes mellitus are knowledgeable about Diabetes and more likely depressed. 10 to 15 percent patients with diabetes have major Depression.[21] Depression associated with social withdrawal disengagement from social activities, patients with increased level of depression report more.[22] Study has shown that in Diabetes Depression is associated with poor glucose control than HbA1c levels. Depression associated with poor physical health.[23] With poor glucose control there are changes in autonomic nervous system hypothalamic adrenal axis and neurotransmitter.[24] According to winokur et al Depression associated with insulin resistance compared with without depression [24]. Depression is directly related to Diabetic complications, retinopathy and macro vascular complications.[25] Depression diabetes and cardiovascular disease are closely related, depression in diabetes increases risk of cardiovascular disease [26,27]. Depression and diabetes associated with decrease in physical activity, smoking and diet.[28] Depression associated with activation of the hypothalamic pituitary adrenal axis and release of cytokines disturbance in sympathetic nervous system and increases the risk of mortality[29] It has been shown that antidepressants and cognitive behavioral therapy reduces HbA1c levels.[30] In this study screening for depression in Diabetes mellitus is

compulsory. Screening, identification and treatment of depression improve symptoms and functional outcome in primary care patients.[31]

keton et al report in a study 43 out of 85 patients incomplete rate of correct recognition depression over a year of study.[31] American diabetic association recommends in DM with poor control should be screened for depression.[32] We found weaker relationship between depression diet, and medication adherence, management of depression in Diabetes mellitus seems to be cost-effective.[33] Missed appointments are associated with increased provider frustration and decreased empathy.[34] It has been found that there is no evidence to suggest that relationship between depression self-care varied as a function of type of diabetes and major depression it was found that severity of depression BMI total fat mass and HbA1C decreased during acute phase treatment and adherence to diet and exercise improved. [35]

Randomized controlled trials suggesting treatment of depression in diabetes has positive effects on diabetes self-care has been lacking trial of antidepressants cognitive behavioral therapy [36], there are data to suggest that Depression is associated with poor blood glucose control [36].

CONCLUSION:

Depression in diabetes is a chronic illness of unknown etiology several neuroendocrine and neurotransmitters abnormalities are same to diabetes and depression. Treatment of depression with antidepressant drugs improve mood and blood glucose level in diabetes mellitus. Glycemic control is improved by antidepressant drugs and anti-diabetic drugs quality of life is improved.

REFERENCES

1. Diabetes care and research in Europe: an action program for the implementation of St. Vincent Declaration for the improvement of diabetes

- care, Copenhagen: WHO Regional office for Europe: 1991.
2. Wild S, Roglic G, Green A, Sicree R, King H. Global prevalence of diabetes; estimates for the year 2000 and projections for 2030, *Diabetes care* 2004;27:1047-53.
 3. Wexler DJ, Grant RW, Wittenberg E, Bosch JL, Cagliero E, Delahanty L, et al. Correlates of health-related quality of life in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetologia* 2006; 49:1489-1497.
 4. Lin EH, Von Korff MV. Mental disorders among persons with diabetes- Results from the world Mental Health Surveys. *J Psychosom Re* 2008; 65:571-580
 5. Fischer L, Skaff MM, Mullan JT, Areant P, Glasgow R, Masharani U. A longitudinal study of affective and anxiety disorders, depressive affect and diabetes distress in adults with type 2 diabetes. *Diabet Med* 2008; 25:1096-1101.
 6. Dimatteo RM, Lepper HS, Croghan TW: Depression is a risk factor for noncompliance with medical treatment: meta-analysis of the effects of anxiety and depression on patient adherence *Arch Int Med* 2000; 160:2101-2101.
 7. Tell-Zenteno JF, Cardiel MH, Risk factors associated with depression in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Arch Med Res* 2002; 33:53-60.
 8. Mezuk B, Eaton W, Albrecht S, Golden SH. Depression and type 2 diabetes over life span, *Diabetes Care* 2008; 31:2383-2390.
 9. Nouwen A, Winkley K, Twisk J, Lloyd CE, Peyrot M, Ismail K, et al. Type 2 diabetes mellitus as a risk factor for the onset of depression: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetologia* 2010; 53:2480-2486.
 10. Talbot F, Nauwen A. A review of the relationship between depression and diabetes in adults; there is link? *Diabetes Care* 2000; 23(10):1556-1562.
 11. Knol MJ, Twisk JW, Beekman AT, Heine RJ, Snoek FJ, Pouwer F. Depression as a risk factor for the onset of type 2 diabetes mellitus. A meta-analysis, *Diabetologia* 2006; 49(5):837-845.
 12. Musselman DL, Betan E, Larsen H, Phillips LS. Relationship depression to diabetes types 1 and 2; epidemiology, biology and treatment, *Boil Psych* 2003; 54(3):317-329.
 13. Lustman PJ, Anderson RJ, Freedland KE, de Groot M, Carney RM, Clouse RE. Depression and poor glycemic control; a meta-analytic review of literature, *Diabetes Care* 2000; (7):934-942.
 14. Wagner JA, Abbot GL, Heapy A, Yong L. Depressive symptoms and diabetes control in African Americans, *J Immigr Minor Health* 2009; 11(1):66-70.
 15. Gonzalez S, Safren SA, Delahanty LM, Cagliero E, Waxler DJ, Meigs JB, et al., Symptoms of depression prospectively predict poorer self-care in patients with type 2 diabetes, *Diabetic. Med* 2008; 25 (9):1102-1107.
 16. Gonzalez JS, Peyrot M, McCarl LA, Collins EM, Serpa L, Mimiaga MJ, et al. Depression and diabetes treatment nonadherence: a meta-analysis. *Diabetes Care* 2008; 31(12):1102-1107.
 17. Lin EH, Katon W, Von Korff M, Ruttler C, Simon GE, Oliver M, et al. Relationship of depression and diabetes self-care, medication adherence, and preventive care. *Diabetes Care* 2004;27(9): 2154-2160.
 18. The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial Research Group: The effect of intensive treatment of diabetes on the development and progression of long-term complications in insulin dependent diabetes mellitus. *N Engl J Med* 1993; 329:977-86.
 19. Hamilton W, Round A, Sharp D: Patient, hospital, and general practitioner characteristics associated with non-attendance a cohort study: *Br J Gen Pract* 2003; 52:317-319.
 20. Robin L, Ned Regier D. *Aed Psychiatric Disorders in America: The Epidemiological Catchment Area Study*. New York, NY Free Press 1991;
 21. Lustman PJ, Clouse RE, Freedland KE. Management of major depression in adults in adults with diabetes: implications of recent medical trials. *Semin Clin Neuropsychiatry* 1998;3102-114.
 22. Lustman PS, Clouse RE, Carney RM. Depression and the report in of diabetes symptoms. *Int J Psychiatry Med* 1988; 18295-303.
 23. Katon W J The effect of major depression on medical chronic illness. *Semin Neuropsychiatry* 1998; 382-86.
 24. Winouker A, Maislin G, Phillips JL, Amsterdam JD. Insulin resistance after oral glucose tolerance testing in patients with major depression. *Am J Psychiat* 1988; 145325-330.

25. Carney RM, Freedland KE, Lustman PJ, Griffith LS. Depression and coronary artery disease in diabetic patients: a 10-year follow up. *Psychosom Med* 1985; 47:372-38
26. Black SA, Markides KS, Ray LA. Depression predicts increased incidence of adverse health outcomes in older Mexicans Americans with type 2 Diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2003; 26:2822-2828.
27. Lin EH, Heckbert SR, Rutter CM, Caton WJ, Ciechanowski P, et al. Depression and increased mortality in diabetes: unexpected cause of death. *Annals Family Medicine* 2009;7: 414-421.
28. Gonzalez Js, Peyrot M, McCarl LA, Collins EM, Serpa L, et al. Depression and diabetes treatment nonadherence: a meta-analysis. *Diabetes Care* 2008;31: 2398-2403.
29. de jonge P, Rosmalen JG, Kema IP, Dooranpos B, van Melle JP, et al. Psychophysiological biomarker explaining the association between Depression and prognosis in coronary artery patients: a critical review of literature. *Neuroscience and behavioral Reviews* 2010; 35:84-90.
30. Lustman PJ, Griffith LS, Clouse RE. Effects of nortriptyline on depression and glycemic control in diabetes: results of double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Psychosom Med* 1997; 59:241-250.
31. Katon WJ, Von Korff M, Lin E, et al. Population-based care of depression: effective disease management strategies to decrease prevalence. *Gen Hosp Psychiat* 1997; 19:169-178.
32. Lustman PJ, Freedland KE, Griffith LS, Clouse RE: Fluoxetine for depression in diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2000; 23:618-623.
33. Lustman PJ, Griffith LS, Freedland KE, Clouse RE: Course of major depression in diabetes. *Gen Hosp Psychiat* 1997; 19:138-143.
34. Lustman PJ, Griffith LS, Freedland KE, Kissel SS, Clouse RE. Cognitive behavior therapy for depression in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Ann intern Med* 1998; 129:613-621.
35. Fris R, Nanjundappa G, Diabetes, depression and employment status, *Soc Sci Med* 1986;23:471-75.
36. Lustman PJ, Griffith LS, Clouse RE, Cryer PE. Psychiatric illness in diabetes, relationship to symptoms and glucose control. *J Nerv Ment Dis* 1986;174, 736-42.